

Data modelling in the National Edition of Aldo Moro's works

Technical report

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Introduction

The National Edition of Aldo Moro's works¹ is a critical digital edition of the published and unpublished texts of the famous Italian politicians, with the objective of providing a cultural product that is universally available to all citizens and proposing a new standard for national and international research in political communication. The Edition is completely digital and can be explored through multiple different criteria based on the intertextual and contextual elements related to Moro's works, identified by those researchers who annotated them.

The aim of this report is to describe the data modelling process of the Edition. In particular, it focuses on describing the main models that were used to represent textual, contextual, and bibliographic information related to Moro's works. Although it is based on the Edition Scientific Committee's specific needs, other people could benefit from this document, since it defines an example of conceptual modelling that can be easily replicated in other projects as well.

The diagrams presented in this document have been generated by using the Graphic Framework for OLW Ontologies (Graffoo)², an open-source tool for visually representing conceptual models.

A series of namespace abbreviations have been used to refer to specific conceptual models in textual descriptions and diagrams. The complete namespace declaration of each model can be found in Table 1.

¹ <https://aldomorodigitale.unibo.it/>

² <https://essepuntato.it/graffoo/specification/>

Prefix	Model	URI
biro	Bibliographic Reference Ontology	http://purl.org/spar/biro/
c4o	Citation Counting and Context Characterization Ontology	http://purl.org/spar/c4o/
dcterms	Dublin Core Terms	http://purl.org/dc/terms/
deo	Document Elements Ontology	http://purl.org/spar/deo/
doco	Document Components Ontology	http://purl.org/spar/doco/
fabio	FRBR-aligned Bibliographic Ontology	http://purl.org/spar/fabio/
foaf	Friend of a Friend	http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/
frbr	Expression of Core FRBR Concepts in RDF	http://purl.org/vocab/frbr/core#
mrsv	Moro Roles Vocabulary	https://www.w3id.org/moro/voc/roles/
msv	Moro Subjects Vocabulary	https://www.w3id.org/moro/voc/subjects/
mtv	Moro Types Vocabulary	https://www.w3id.org/moro/voc/types/
owl	OWL 2 Schema	http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#
pro	Publishing Roles Ontology	http://purl.org/spar/pro/
pso	Publishing Status Ontology	http://purl.org/spar/pso/
rdf	RDF Syntax	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#
rdfs	RDF Schema	http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#
skos	Simple Knowledge Organization System	http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#
ti	Time Interval	http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/cp/owl/time#
tvcc	Time-indexed Value in Context	http://www.essepuntato.it/2012/04/tvc/
xsd	XML Schema Definition	http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#

Table 1. The namespace declaration of the used models.

The standards

Resource Description Framework

Resource Description Framework (RDF)³ is a World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)⁴ standard which allows representing, describing, and publishing data on the Web in an accessible and machine-readable format. In particular, RDF allows one to identify, disambiguate, connect, and publish anything it is possible to say something about, in a language that can be understood by humans, but also processable by software agents.

RDF is based on three fundamental concepts, as shown in Figure 1:

- *Resource*: any entity it is possible to say something about;
- *Property*: an attribute or characteristic of a resource, or a semantic relationship existing between two resources;
- *Statement*: the structure made up by a resource (subject), a property (predicate), and either another resource or a value related to the subject in terms of that property (object).

Figure 1. The elements which constitute the foundation of the RDF model: resource, property, and statement.

Subject and predicate are always identified by their respective Uniform Resource Identifier (URI)⁵, unique and permanent pointers that help machines understand and contextualize assertions. The object can be identified by its URI or can be represented by

³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/>

⁴ <https://www.w3.org/>

⁵ <https://www.w3.org/Addressing/URL/uri-spec.html>

a simple value (literal, numeric, temporal, etc.) that expresses a subject’s attribute (such as a name, a title, or their age).

Figure 2 shows an example of how we used RDF to model information contained in the Edition. A work (identified by the URI <https://w3id.org/moro/enoam/data/110001>) is the subject of two statements:

- the work was created by (<http://purl.org/dc/terms/creator>) Aldo Moro (<https://w3id.org/moro/enoam/data/aldo-moro>);
- the work is entitled (<http://purl.org/dc/terms/title>) “Saluto” (literal value).

Figure 2. Two RDF statements about a work: 1) the work was created by Aldo Moro; 2) the work is entitled “Saluto”. Each resource and property that is part of the statements is identified by its respective Uniform Resource Identifier.

The Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records

The Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR)⁶, proposed by the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA), is a conceptual model to describe bibliographic resources and metadata related to them, without specific

⁶ <https://www.ifla.org/publications/functional-requirements-for-bibliographic-records>

limitations in terms of implementation, and that can be applied to both physical objects and digital resources.

FRBR describes a resource from four different conceptual viewpoints, interconnected and defined by the following categories:

- *Work*, the abstract entity representing the essence of the intellectual/artistic product as it formed in the author’s mind, realized through one or more Expressions;
- *Expression*, the abstract entity representing the content of the intellectual/artistic product that it takes on so as to be realized and communicated to others, embodied by one or more Manifestations;
- *Manifestation*, the concrete entity representing the materialization of the Expression in a specific format, exemplified by one or more Items;
- *Item*, the concrete entity representing the single copy, tangible and localized, of a certain Manifestation.

Figure 3 shows an example of how FRBR can be applied to the Edition’s contents. In particular, FRBR allows making a distinction between the different notions of “work” and their specific characteristics in terms of abstract creation (“Saluto” as it was conceived in the author’s mind), intellectual content (the text of “Saluto”), publication (the version of “Saluto” that was published on the Edition’s website), and the single copy (the file downloaded on one’s personal computer).

Figure 3. The conceptual levels of a work according to the FRBR model.

Each point of view is related to the other through a specific conceptual relationship, forming a continuous flow from Work to Item and vice versa. Thus FRBR allows one to describe a resource contained in the Edition and its relationships with other resources in

a way that is more expressive, detailed, and dynamic, since it breaks down the semantic ambiguities that characterize a resource into separate concepts.

The knowledge organization systems

A knowledge organization system is a schema that models the structure of an organized set of information about a given knowledge domain. It classifies a series of concepts to define, manage, and retrieve information.

To model and manage the Edition's data, we used to main types of knowledge organization systems: controlled vocabularies and ontologies.

Controlled vocabularies

A *controlled vocabulary* is a knowledge organization system made up by words and/or expressions used to index and retrieve contents through navigation and search activities. The aim of a controlled vocabulary is to organize information and distribute standardized terminology for cataloguing and retrieving such information. In particular, a controlled vocabulary defines standardized terms to be used in a specific domain, maps them to their respective variants and synonyms, and organizes them into logical structures according to precise conceptual rules.

With the adoption of the Linked Open Data (LOD)⁷ paradigm, the W3C model Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS)⁸ has become the main standard for publishing, sharing, and linking machine-readable knowledge organization systems on the Web.

For the Edition, we developed three SKOS-based controlled vocabularies, which allowed us to model the concepts related to Moro's roles, his works' subjects, and their document types. In particular, the controlled vocabularies are:

- *Moro Roles Vocabulary* (MRV)⁹;
- *Moro Subjects Vocabulary* (MSV)¹⁰;

⁷ <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData>

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/2009/08/skos-reference/skos.html>

⁹ <https://www.w3id.org/moro/voc/roles>

¹⁰ <https://www.w3id.org/moro/voc/subjects>

- *Moro Types Vocabulary* (MTV)¹¹.

Similarly to the *Iconclass*¹² classification scheme, our vocabularies are not based on fully-fledged terminology since the terms requested to be used tend to be verbose and detailed. Instead, the vocabularies' concepts are identified by alphanumeric codes accompanied by textual labels written in natural language to document their meaning. For example, the concept of "Diocesan delegate of Catholic Youth's Aspirants" (one of the roles held by Aldo Moro) is represented by the code `ro1e01`, where:

- `[ro1e]` denotes the *top concept* that works as the vocabulary's access point (possible values are: `ro1e`, `subject`, or `type`);
- `[01]` represents a number, univocally and arbitrarily assigned, that allows the concept to be referred to univocally.

Each vocabulary, encoded according to the RDF data model through its Terse RDF Triple Language (Turtle)¹³ serialization, is composed of:

- a list of prefixes that refer to the reused models' URIs;
- a series of concepts that populate the vocabulary. Each concept, modelled as an instance of `skos:Concept`, is identified by a series of natural language labels (`skos:prefLabel`, `skos:altLabel`) and characterized by semantic relations with other elements of the vocabulary, such as `skos:broader` (hierarchical relation that connects the concept to a broader one) and `skos:inScheme` (a relation that connects the concept to the vocabulary itself). Finally, each concept is documented by a natural language description through the property `skos:definition`;
- the *top concept*, the semantically broadest concept within the vocabulary, which acts as access point to the vocabulary itself. It is identified by some natural language labels (`rdfs:label` and `skos:prefLabel`), documented by definitions and notes (`skos:definition` and `skos:scopeNote`) and related to other vocabulary elements through other properties, such as

¹¹ <https://www.w3id.org/moro/voc/types>

¹² <http://www.iconclass.nl/>

¹³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/turtle/>

`skos:inScheme`, `skos:narrower` (the inverse property of `skos:broader`), and `skos:topConceptOf` (a property that defines the vocabulary access point);

- the vocabulary itself, modelled as an instance of `skos:ConceptScheme` and characterized by properties about documentation (`skos:definition`, `skos:scopeNote`), access point (`skos:hasTopConcept`, the inverse property of `skos:topConceptOf`), and the minimum necessary metadata to identify and localize it, such as its title (`dcterms:title`), authors (`dc:creator` and `dc:contributor`), publication date (`dc:date`), and identifier (`dcterms:identifier`).

The vocabularies' quality was validated was checked by using a series of tools developed to validate SKOS-based resources written in RDF. In particular, we used *Skosify*¹⁴, *SKOS Play!*¹⁵, and *SKOS Testing Tool*¹⁶.

Ontologies

An *ontology* is the most complex and semantically rich type of knowledge organization system and consists of a semantic model that describes a finite part of a specific domain in a formal way by identifying a series of concepts (classes of objects) and the relations existing between them.

Generally speaking, ontological modelling is a method to organize discrete facts into a coherent information system, in which data is structured, managed, and made available to end users. An ontology can be used to inject machine-readable meaning into any kind of information resource, so as to allow complex operations such as automatic disambiguation, logical inference, and cross-referenced research from different sources.

The most widely used standards for ontology development are the Resource Description Framework Schema (RDFS)¹⁷ and the Web Ontology Language (OWL)¹⁸, both extensions of

¹⁴ <https://seco.cs.aalto.fi/tools/skosify/>

¹⁵ <https://labs.sparna.fr/skos-play/home>

¹⁶ <https://labs.sparna.fr/skos-testing-tool/>

¹⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>

¹⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-overview/>

the RDF model. These standards provide ways to organize data as graph structures based on RDF statements.

Some ontologies were reused to describe Aldo Moro's works, and the intertextual and contextual information that characterize them. In particular, the following models have been reused:

- Bibliographic Reference Ontology (BiRO)¹⁹, an ontology to define records and bibliographic references, and their compilation in collections and bibliographic lists;
- Citation Counting and Context Characterization Ontology (C4O)²⁰, an ontology to characterize bibliographic citations in terms of their presence within a document;
- Discourse Elements Ontology (DEO)²¹, an ontology to describe rhetorical elements of a bibliographic document;
- Document Components Ontology (DoCO)²², an ontology to describe elements that make up a bibliographic element;
- Dublin Core Metadata Terms (DCTerms)²³, an ontology that implements metadata definitions managed by the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative;
- FRBR-aligned Bibliographic Ontology (FaBiO)²⁴, an ontology that extends the FRBR model to describe and publish bibliographic documents;
- Friend Of A Friend vocabulary (FOAF)²⁵, an ontology to describe agents (people, organizations, etc.) and their relations with other agents, documents, and information objects;
- Expression of Core FRBR Concepts in RDF (FRBRcore)²⁶, an ontology that implements the FRBR model into RDF;

¹⁹ <http://purl.org/spar/biro>

²⁰ <http://purl.org/spar/c4o>

²¹ <http://purl.org/spar/deo>

²² <http://purl.org/spar/doco>

²³ <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>

²⁴ <http://purl.org/spar/fabio>

²⁵ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>

²⁶ <http://purl.org/vocab/frbr/core#>

- Publishing Roles Ontology (PRO)²⁷, an ontology to describe situations in which some agents hold roles during certain intervals of time and within certain contexts;
- Publishing Status Ontology (PSO)²⁸, an ontology to describe the publication state held by a document during each phase of its publication;
- Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS)²⁹, a model to publish, share, and connect knowledge organization systems on the Web;
- Time Interval pattern (TI)³⁰, an ontology to model time periods;
- Time-indexed Value in Context pattern (TVC)³¹, an ontology to describe situations in which an agent holds a certain value in a certain period of time and within a certain context.

The results

The documents' structure

We modeled the documents to be published on the Edition by using Resource Description Framework in Attributes (RDFa)³², an RDF serialization which allows adding structured data to HTML pages through a series of specific attributes.

Each document is characterized by:

- basic *bibliographic information*, such as the license, the Digital Object Identifier (DOI)³³, the respective page on the Edition's website, and the bibliographic citation;
- a series of *mentions* to people, places, and organizations, *bibliographic references* to works cited by Aldo Moro, and *quotations*;

²⁷ <http://purl.org/spar/pro>

²⁸ <http://purl.org/spar/pso>

²⁹ <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core>

³⁰ <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/cp/owl/timeinterval.owl#>

³¹ <http://purl.org/spar/tvc/>

³² <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdfa-primer/>

³³ <https://www.doi.org/index.html>

- information about *mentioned entities*, such as attested forms, authority control, and controlled forms of people's names;
- a series of *notes* that make up the critical commentary made by both researchers and Aldo Moro himself;
- a series of *paragraphs*, uniquely identified and numbered, containing the document's text.

The text of each work is contained in both paragraphs and notes. Mentions, bibliographic references, and quotations are paragraph elements that were marked up by researchers using the KWICKWOCKWAC³⁴ web application.

We modeled the mentions and the notes as text fragments enclosed by a series of `` elements contained in the `<body>` element. Each `` is characterized by a series of attributes that reproduce RDF syntax within HTML code: `@about` (subject); `@property` (property); `@resource` (entity object) or `@content` (value object).

Moreover, each `` represents an instance of a certain ontological class, which can be either `doco:TextChunk` (quotation), `biro:BibliographicReference` (bibliographic reference), or `o deo:Reference` (mention). This information is expressed by using the attribute `@typeof` (the RDFa equivalent of `rdf:type`). If a `` represents a mention or a bibliographic reference, the values of its `@property` and `@resource` attributes are `dcterms:references` and the mentioned entity's URI, respectively.

Notes are represented by a series of `` elements contained in an `` element, characterized by a `@id` with a value expressing the type of the notes it contains (`curatorNotes` for notes made by researchers, and `moroNotes` for notes made by Moro). Similarly to `` elements described above, each `` element represents an instance of an ontological class (in this case `fabio:Comment`), characterized by the same `@about`, `@property`, and `@resource` attributes. The values of the `@property` and `@resource` attributes, in this case, are `dcterms:creator` and the note author's URI (either the researcher who curated the document or Aldo Moro, according to the note's type).

Mentioned entities (people, organizations, places, and bibliographic resources) are collected within the `<head>` element. Each mentioned entity is modelled as a `<meta>`

³⁴ <https://aldomorodigitale.unibo.it/markup>

element representing an RDF statement about that entity, by using the same attributes mentioned above (@about, @property, and @resource/@content). Each entity is expressed as an instance of person (foaf:Person), organization (foaf:Organization), place (dcterms:Location), or bibliographic resources (fabio:Expression), by using the @typeof attribute. Each entity is identified by a natural language label by using the @property and @content attributes with rdfs:label and a string of text (a name, a title, a citation, ecc.). Moreover, each entity can be aligned with the respective record on Wikidata to enforce authority control and link it to external information by using the @property and @resource properties, with owl:sameAs and the corresponding Wikidata entity's URI as their respective values. Finally, if an entity is a person, it is characterized by a controlled form of its name (“[Family name], [Name]”) by using the @property and @content attributes, with skos:prefLabel and a string of text containing the controlled form as their respective values.

The information encoded in the documents through RDFa syntax were added to an RDF dataset as well, taking the content of the statements and enriching it with more relations between entities, and converting them in Turtle syntax. Figure 4 illustrates the entities and relationships that make up the information contained in the dataset.

Figure 4. The Graffoo diagram shows the relations between mentions, bibliographic references, notes, mentioned entities, and bibliographic resources.

The bibliographic resource understood as Expression, that is intellectual content (`fabio:Expression`), is made up by (`frbr:part`) instances of four classes that represent mentions (`deo:Reference`), bibliographic reference (`biro:BibliographicReference`), footnotes (`fabio:Comment`), and quotations (`doco:TextChunk`). The Expression is related to the Manifestation, the bibliographic resource understood as the digital document that was marked up by researchers and published on the Edition (`fabio:Manifestation`), through the property `frbr:embodiment`.

An instance of `fabio:Comment` is created by (`dcterms:creator`) an instance of `foaf:Person`. An instance of `biro:BibliographicReference` refers to an Expressio

(`fabio:Expression`) through the property `biro:references`. The textual content of mentions, references, footnotes, and quotations is expressed through the property `c4o:hasContent`.

Bibliographic metadata

Metadata are data that describe the content, structure, and context of a resource (a document, a dataset, an image, etc.), that allow it to be managed, accessed, and curated in time. In particular, descriptive metadata contain information that is necessary to describe a document and its bibliographic and historical context, so as to be easily identified, retrieved, and consulted.

Metadata related to the Edition's works were modeled by reusing well-known conceptual schemas (such as Dublin Core), to build a solid and extensible foundation for the knowledge base.

During the markup phase, researchers added metadata to their respective works by filling a form in the KWICKWOCKWAC web application, so as to store them in a specific MongoDB³⁵ database. Then, we gathered those metadata into an RDF dataset in the form of statements written in Turtle. Finally, we enriched the dataset with structured data contained in the single documents (such as mentions, notes, etc.), in order to have a complete and up-to-date knowledge base.

Table 2 shows the metadata used to describe the Edition's works. Each field is accompanied by a brief natural language description, an example, and the respective ontological property that expresses its meaning.

³⁵ <https://www.mongodb.com/>

Metadata field	Description	Example	RDF property
<i>ident</i>	A numerical string that identifies the document within the collection. It follows the scheme: nSection_nVolume_nTome_nDocument	1_4_2_221	dcterms:identifier
<i>title</i>	The document's title.	Una pacata riflessione	dcterms:title
<i>author</i>	The name of the document's author.	Aldo Moro	dcterms:creator
<i>roleList</i>	A list of roles held by the author during the time the document was created/published for the first time.	Journalist and political commentator	pro:withRole
<i>curator</i>	The full name of the researcher who curated the document.	Chiara Zampieri	dcterms:contributor
<i>docstatus</i>	The publication status of the document (either published or unpublished).	Published	pso:withStatus
<i>abstract</i>	A high-level description of the document.	Aldo Moro interviene sul quotidiano milanese il 2 settembre 1977 sul tema della fuga di Herbert Kappler [...]	dcterms:abstract
<i>eventDate</i>	The creation or publication date of the document.	1976-3-20	dcterms:date
<i>eventPlace</i>	The place where the event described in the document has taken place, if applicable.	Roma	dcterms:spatial
<i>provenance</i>	A list of citation strings of primary or secondary sources of the document.	Aldo Moro. Scritti e discorsi. Volume sesto: 1974-1978, a cura di G. Rossini, Roma, Cinque lune, 1990	dcterms:provenance
<i>doctypeList</i>	A list of document types (e.g. Interview, Book, etc.)	Magazine article	dcterms:type
<i>doctopicList</i>	A list of document subjects (e.g. Law, Society, etc.)	Internal policy	dcterms:subject
<i>additionalNotes</i>	Further observations about other aspects of the document to highlight (ex. the presence of the author's signature)	Il documento riporta la firma autografa "ALDO MORO"	skos:note

Table 2. The list of metadata fields filled by the researchers to describe the Edition's works.

Metadata are distributed between three FRBR levels that were considered to describe the Edition's works (Work, Expression, and Manifestation). These levels are interlinked through their respective properties provided by FRBRcore: a Work is realized (`frbr:realization`) through an Expression, which in turn is embodied (`frbr:embodiment`) in a Manifestation. Work and Manifestation are linked through the property `fabio:hasManifestation`.

Metadata at the Work level (`fabio:Work`) are: the title (`dcterms:title`), the author (`dcterms:creator`), the subject (`dcterms:subject`, whose range is an instance of `msv:Subject`, extracted from the controlled vocabulary MSV), and the author's role. The author's role, understood as bibliographic metadata contextualized in a certain period of time, was realized through the use of the Publishing Roles Ontology (PRO). According to PRO, a role in time (`pro:RoleInTime`) is a situation that describes a role (specifically for the Edition, an instance of `mrsv:Role`, a class extracted from the controlled vocabulary MRV) that an agent (Aldo Moro) holds for a certain period on time (`ti:TimeInterval`) and in relation to a certain context (`fabio:Work`).

Metadata at the Expression level (`fabio:Expression`) are: the researcher who curated the document (`dcterms:contributor`, whose range is an instance of `foaf:Person`), the abstract describing it (`dcterms:abstract`), its type (`dcterms:type`, whose range is an instance of `mtv:Type`, a class extracted from the controlled vocabulary MTV), the date of creation or first publication (`dcterms:date`), the place of the event described in it (`dcterms:spatial`), the publication status, and additional notes (`skos:note`). The publication status was expressed by using the Publishing Status Ontology (PSO), according to which a status in time (`pso>StatusInTime`) is a situation that describes a state (an instance of `pso:Status`) held by a publishable entity (the Expression, in this case).

Metadata at the Manifestation level (`fabio:Manifestation`) are: the identifier (`dcterms:identifier`), converted into a string containing the document's DOI during the document processing phase, and the sources (`dcterms:provenance`). The list of document sources as metadata of the single work was realized through the use of `dcterms:ProvenanceStatement`, a class that expresses a provenance statement characterized by a series of properties: the researcher who created it (`dcterms:creator`), its creation date (`dcterms:created`), the source that provides the theoretical foundation of said statement (`dcterms:source`, whose range is an instance

of `fabio:Expression`), and its textual content (`c4o:hasContent`), which is the metadata value originally inserted by the researcher. The instance of `fabio:Expression` that indicates the document source is the bibliographic resource identified by the textual content of the statement, repeated also as a citation to the work itself (`dcterms:bibliographicCitation`).

Figure 5. The Grafoo diagram illustrates the relation between the livelli concettuali di un'opera di Moro e i metadata che ne descrivono il contesto.

During the data processing phase, additional information were added to the Manifestation level:

- the license (`dcterms:rights`): works published on the Edition are distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution – Non Commercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)³⁶ which allows one to freely access, use, reproduce, distribute, transmit, communicate and show them as well as produce and distribute derivative works with any directly or indirectly commercial use strictly forbidden on the condition

³⁶ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/deed.it>

that the authors' moral rights are safeguarded and that the original sources are adequately acknowledged and cited;

- the bibliographic citation (`dcterms:bibliographicCitation`), whose value follows this model:
 - Moro, Aldo, <Title>, in Aldo Moro, Edizione Nazionale delle Opere di Aldo Moro, <Section>, <Section title>, <Volume>, <Volume title>, edited by <Volume curators>, curated by <Researcher>, Bologna, University of Bologna, 2021. DOI: <DOI>
- the link to the work's webpage on the Edition's website (`dcterms:relation`).